

A Fast Hexagonal Sigma-Delta Strategy with DC-Bus Balancing for Three-Level Wide-Bandgap T-Type Converters

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Abstract—The efficiency of wide-bandgap (WBG) power converters can be significantly enhanced using high-frequency modulation techniques. This article presents a novel hexagonal sigma-delta ($H-\Sigma\Delta$) modulation designed for high-frequency three-level T-type converters employing WBG semiconductors. To simplify implementation and reduce computational burden, a fast-processing quantizer is proposed. The proposed $H-\Sigma\Delta$ strategy operates with a variable switching frequency, minimising switching losses compared to conventional pulse-width modulation (PWM) techniques, while suppressing low-frequency neutral-point voltage oscillations. The behaviour is analysed via simulation and experimentally validated on a T-type converter using silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFETs and gallium nitride (GaN) e-HEMTs. Compared against Carrier-Based PWM (CB-PWM) and Modified Sinusoidal PWM (M-SPWM) under identical conditions, experimental results demonstrate that the proposed $H-\Sigma\Delta$ modulation achieves superior performance, reaching a peak efficiency of 95.92%. Additionally, it virtually eliminates low-frequency DC-link oscillations. Regarding power quality, the modulation mitigates Common-Mode Voltage (CMV) spikes and exhibits a favourable spectral profile when compared to the limits suggested by IEC 61000-3-2 and IEC 55025 emission standards. The analysis confirms the proposed strategy as a highly effective solution for maximising the efficiency and electromagnetic compatibility of WBG-based T-type converters.

Index Terms—Fast quantizer, modulation technique, power converter, power electronics, sigma-delta ($\Sigma\Delta$) modulation, T-type converter, vector quantization, wide-bandgap (WBG) semiconductors.

I. INTRODUCTION

MULTILEVEL converters are highly attractive for medium- and high-voltage power applications due to their ability to handle higher power levels with improved efficiency and reduced harmonic distortion. Among the various multilevel converter topologies, the neutral-point clamped (NPC), flying capacitor, cascaded H-bridge, and T-type converters have been widely applied in numerous applications [1], [2]. While these topologies have been extensively studied, the emergence of wide-bandgap (WBG) semiconductors has

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a T-type converter based on SiC and GaN semiconductors.

significantly enhanced their performance characteristics. WBG semiconductors, such as gallium nitride (GaN) and silicon carbide (SiC), offer superior properties compared to traditional silicon-based devices, enabling the development of high-power-density converters capable of operating at extremely high switching frequencies (>100 kHz) with significantly reduced losses [3], [4]. Currently, GaN devices are primarily limited to low-voltage applications (<650 V), whereas SiC devices are preferred for high-voltage operations due to their higher breakdown voltage and thermal performance [3]. The integration of WBG semiconductors has already demonstrated remarkable success in various power electronics applications, including on-board chargers [5], electric vehicles [6], [7], and active power filters [8].

Nevertheless, the industry is not fully taking advantage of WBG properties. To maximise their potential, specifically enabling high-frequency switching with minimal losses, WBG-based power converters, such as the hybrid T-type converter depicted in Fig. 1, should employ modulation techniques optimised for performance at these elevated frequencies. Many modulation techniques for three-level T-type converters have been proposed in the literature. In [9], the authors proposed a reduced-common-voltage carrier-based discontinuous pulse-width modulation (RCMV-CB-DPWM). This modulation uses zero-sequence voltage injection and a flexible carrier waveform arrangement to reduce common-mode voltage (CMV), switching losses, and eliminate DC offset from the neutral point (NP) voltage simultaneously. A similar algorithm was

presented in [10]. This article introduces a carrier-based discontinuous pulse-width modulation (CB-DPWM) with an NP voltage balancing strategy. This method also employs the injection of zero-sequence voltages to balance the NP voltage. Moreover, this modulation can be used in parallel systems to suppress NP voltage ripples and circulating currents. Reference [11] presented a carrier-based discontinuous space-vector pulse-width modulation (RCMV-DSVPWM) for CMV reduction. This strategy analyses the CMV and discards high CMV vectors to form new space vector diagrams. The authors propose a method to simplify subsector judgement and modify the modulation waves for carrier-based implementation. Lak *et al.* [12] proposed a hybrid carrier-based pulse-width modulation method for T-type three-level inverters to achieve CMV elimination and active NP balancing control simultaneously. The strategy employs medium vector PWM (MVPWM) patterns to maintain a constant CMV (zero in steady state). Moreover, it combines high/low triangle PWM and MVPWM to balance NP voltage during transients. Lak *et al.* [13] also introduced a hybrid method for a T-type three-level photovoltaic inverter, integrating MVPWM and discontinuous PWM (DPWM) methods. The proposed hybrid approach aims to eliminate leakage current and balance NP. MVPWM is used in normal states to suppress leakage current, and DPWM in unbalanced states to balance NP. In [14], the authors proposed a hybrid active PWM strategy with dual-mode modulation waves for a T-type three-level converter in aircraft turboelectric propulsion systems. This technique aims to reduce switching losses and achieve capacitor voltage balancing, using a coordinate system to define the modulation wave shape composed of two simple control variables. Finally, article [15] proposed an optimisation of symmetrical space vector PWM (SVPWM). Instead of balancing NP, this method optimises symmetrical SVPWM to work with unbalanced voltages. This modulation aims to reduce current harmonics and maintain a high linear modulation index. However, a significant limitation in the previous studies is that these modulation techniques have been validated at relatively low switching frequencies, typically not exceeding 30 kHz. Consequently, the specific challenges and trade-offs associated with the high-frequency operation capabilities of WBG devices remain largely unaddressed.

Sigma-delta ($\Sigma\Delta$) modulations are particularly appealing due to their spread-spectrum characteristics. These techniques exhibit variable switching frequencies, which result in reduced EMIs and lower losses compared to conventional modulation strategies, such as space vector pulse-width modulation (SVPWM) [16]. Recently, $\Sigma\Delta$ techniques have been successfully applied to two-level three-phase converters [8], [16], [17] and extended to two-level five-phase converters [18]. However, extending the application of H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations to multilevel converters introduces significant technical challenges. Specifically, multilevel topologies have a substantially higher number of switching states compared to two-level converters. Thus, H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategies must be adapted to handle this increased complexity and incorporate the additional control logic required to manage redundant vectors.

This article proposes a novel H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation strategy for

Fig. 2. Three-level sigma-delta loop. The nominal value of all gains is unity.

three-level T-type converters using wide-bandgap semiconductors. Furthermore, the proposed strategy can be easily adapted to work with NPC converters. The proposed modulation allows:

- 1) working with a variable switching frequency and consequently reducing the switching losses;
- 2) enhancing power quality by mitigating low-order harmonics and reducing CMV;
- 3) eliminating the low-frequency oscillations of the neutral-point voltage.

Furthermore, we propose a fast processing quantizer for the three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique to simplify its implementation and reduce the number of mathematical operations of the proposed modulation. The impact of the three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategy is evaluated based on simulation studies using MATLAB/Simulink and PLECS software. Finally, the results are experimentally validated by implementing the proposed technique.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section II introduces the three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategy, analyses its basis, and details the implementation of its fast-processing quantizer and DC-bus balancing algorithm. Section III examines the characteristics and performance of the proposed modulation through simulations. Section IV provides experimental validation of the aforementioned results, showing the impact of the modulation technique on a real T-type power converter. Finally, Section V concludes this article.

II. PROPOSED SIGMA-DELTA STRATEGY

The proposed three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation shares the modulation loop with its two-level equivalent (see Fig. 2). To analyse this modulation, it is essential to define the plane $P = \{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid \gamma = 0\}$. Then, $T: \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow P$ is defined as

$$T = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

which is a simplified Clarke's transformation.

This modulation operates within the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ reference frame, requiring the conversion of the reference vector into these coordinates using the transformation matrix T . The loop's operation is similar to other $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations: when V_{ref} is within P , the reference vector is compared with the quantizer

 Fig. 3. Three-level vector diagram divided into sectors according to H- $\Sigma\Delta$.

outputs, and the resulting errors are integrated. These integrated errors are inputs to the quantizer, whose outputs will be compared with the next reference vector. Additional integrators can be included in the loop before the quantizer to enhance the modulation (see Fig. 2). However, a maximum of two integrators should be used, as the modulation becomes noisy with three or more integrators [19]. Before each integration, adjustable gains (G_1, G_2) are applied. As analysed in [17], [19], these gains affect output noise and system stability. Therefore, they are nominally set near unity, although slight empirical fine-tuning may be required. The equation describing an N-loop $\Sigma\Delta$ is:

$$V'_x(z) = V_x(z)z^{-1} + e_x(z)(1 - z^{-1})^N \quad (2)$$

where $x = \{\alpha, \beta\}$, and N is the number of integrators.

The main innovation of this modulation is the quantizer, which divides the P -plane into 19 Voronoi regions corresponding to the power converter's switching vectors (see Fig. 3). Since the quantizer output is restricted to these 19 discrete vectors, the feedback loop is inherently bounded. This limits the integrated error, preventing windup and eliminating the need for explicit clamping mechanisms. At each sampling instant, the quantizer identifies the sector where V_{ref} is located and applies the nearest vector. The closest switching vector can be determined using

$$D_i^2 = (V'_{\alpha i} - U_\alpha)^2 + (V'_{\beta i} - U_\beta)^2 \quad (3)$$

where D_i^2 is the Euclidean distance squared from the integrated error (U_α, U_β) to the switching state ($V'_{\alpha i}, V'_{\beta i}$).

The switching vector closest to the reference point is the one with the minimum value of D_i^2 . Due to the high number of possible vectors, this requires a significant amount of calculations. However, the implementation of the quantizer can be optimized using the approach proposed in Section II-A. Once the vector is determined, the switching state is established.

Fig. 4. Three-level vector diagram divided into sectors according to the proposed fast quantizer.

A. Proposed Fast Quantizer

The proposed fast quantizer also divides the P -plane into 19 regions. These regions are bounded by circles and straight lines, as illustrated in Fig. 4. This approach eliminates the need for hexagonal divisions and allows for a more straightforward mathematical expression of the sectors within the P -plane.

The straight lines that divide the P -plane are defined as follows:

$$R_n = \{(\alpha, \beta) \mid \alpha + d_r = 0\}, \quad d_r \in \{0, -0.33, 0.33\} \quad (4)$$

$$S_n = \{(\alpha, \beta) \mid k\alpha - \beta + d_{st} = 0\}, \quad d_{st} \in \{0, 0.385, -0.385\} \quad (5)$$

$$T_n = \{(\alpha, \beta) \mid k\alpha + \beta + d_{st} = 0\}, \quad d_{st} \in \{0, 0.385, -0.385\} \quad (6)$$

where $n = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $k = \tan(\pi/6)$.

By utilizing the previous line expressions, we can define the sectors of P for the proposed modulation technique as follows:

Inner sectors

$$B_0 = \{x \in P \mid \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_i^2\} \quad (7)$$

$$B_1 = \{x \in P \mid (T_0(\alpha) \leq \beta < S_0(\alpha)) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (8)$$

$$B_2 = \{x \in P \mid (\alpha \geq 0) \wedge (\beta \geq S_0(\alpha)) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (9)$$

$$B_3 = \{x \in P \mid (\alpha < 0) \wedge (\beta \geq T_0(\alpha)) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (10)$$

$$B_4 = \{x \in P \mid (\alpha < 0) \wedge (S_0(\alpha) \leq \beta < T_0(\alpha)) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (11)$$

$$B_5 = \{x \in P \mid (\alpha < 0) \wedge (S_0(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (12)$$

$$B_6 = \{x \in P \mid (\alpha \geq 0) \wedge (T_0(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge \wedge (r_i^2 < \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2)\} \quad (13)$$

TABLE I
DETERMINATION OF THE SECTOR IN THREE-LEVEL H- $\Sigma\Delta$

Bit 10	Bit 9	Bit 8	Bit 7	Bit 6	Bit 5	Bit 4	Bit 3	Bit 2	Bit 1	Bit 0	Sector
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	B_{15}
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	B_{14}
0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	B_{13}
0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	-	-	-	B_{12}
0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	B_{11}
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	B_{16}
0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	B_{10}
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	B_{17}
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	B_{18}
0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	-	-	-	B_7
0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	-	-	-	B_8
0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	B_9
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	B_5
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	1	0	B_4
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	1	1	B_3
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	0	B_6
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	1	B_1
1	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	B_2
1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	B_0

where Bit 10 = $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_o^2$, Bit 9 = $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 \leq r_i^2$, Bit 8 = $\alpha \geq -0.33$, Bit 7 = $\alpha \geq 0.33$, Bit 6 = $\beta \geq S_1(\alpha)$, Bit 5 = $\beta \geq S_2(\alpha)$, Bit 4 = $\beta \geq T_1(\alpha)$, Bit 3 = $\beta \geq T_2(\alpha)$, Bit 2 = $\alpha \geq 0$, Bit 1 = $\beta \geq S_0(\alpha)$, Bit 0 = $\beta \geq T_0(\alpha)$ and, "-" indicates that the bit value is irrelevant.

Outer sectors

$$B_7 = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (T_1(\alpha) \leq \beta < S_2(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (14)$$

$$B_8 = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (S_2(\alpha) \leq \beta < S_1(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (15)$$

$$B_9 = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (S_1(\alpha) \leq \beta) \wedge (0.33 \leq \alpha) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (16)$$

$$B_{10} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (-0.33 \leq \alpha < 0.33) \wedge (S_1(\alpha) \leq \beta) \wedge (T_1(\alpha) \leq \beta) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (17)$$

$$B_{11} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (T_1(\alpha) \leq \beta) \wedge (-0.33 > \alpha) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (18)$$

$$B_{12} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (T_2(\alpha) \leq \beta < T_1(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (19)$$

$$B_{13} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (S_1(\alpha) \leq \beta < T_2(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (20)$$

$$B_{14} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (S_2(\alpha) \leq \beta < S_1(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (21)$$

$$B_{15} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (S_2(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge (-0.33 > \alpha) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (22)$$

$$B_{16} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (-0.33 \leq \alpha < 0.33) \wedge (S_2(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge (T_2(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (23)$$

$$B_{17} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (T_2(\alpha) > \beta) \wedge (0.33 \geq \alpha) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (24)$$

$$B_{18} = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in P \mid (T_2(\alpha) \leq \beta < T_1(\alpha)) \wedge (\alpha^2 + \beta^2 > r_o^2)\} \quad (25)$$

Given a point in plane P , the previous expressions determine the region to which it belongs. The procedure for determining the sector is as follows: First, calculate the boundary values of the straight lines R_n , S_n , and T_n from the input. The boundary

points of S_n and T_n depend on α or β and thus must be calculated for each input. In contrast, the boundary value of the R_n lines is constant. In addition, calculate the radius r for each input. Once the boundaries and radius are determined, the quantizer compares the input to them. The comparison result is an 11-bit word used as the address of a read-only memory (ROM). The ROM output is the closest vector, as detailed in Table I. The ROM also determines the coordinates of the applied vector to close the $\Sigma\Delta$ loop.

Unlike two-level $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations, in the proposed technique, determining the nearest vector does not determine the converter's switching state. As depicted in Fig. 4, the vectors corresponding to sectors B_0 through B_6 can be obtained using multiple switching states. The determination of the switching state can be guided by various criteria, such as the reduction of common-mode voltage, the balancing of the DC bus, or the minimization of switching losses. The proposed algorithm consistently selects the vector that optimally balances the DC bus. In contrast, the sectors from B_7 to B_{18} are each achievable through a unique switching state. Consequently, applying these vectors can lead to imbalances in the DC bus. Therefore, the proposed algorithm incorporates a DC bus balancing algorithm, which dynamically selects the appropriate vector based on the state of the DC bus capacitors and the converter output currents.

Table II compares the operations of the proposed fast quantizer against other approaches. Unlike standard $\Sigma\Delta$ quantizers, which compute Euclidean distances via (3) for all potential vectors, and branch-and-bound (B&B) algorithms that restrict candidates via initial comparisons, the proposed method identifies the nearest vector without any distance calculations. Consequently, the fast H- $\Sigma\Delta$ quantizer eliminates subtractions and minimises additions, multiplications, and comparisons. Overall, this approach achieves a 78% and 49% reduction in total arithmetic operations compared to the standard and B&B quantizers, respectively.

TABLE II
OPERATIONS OF THE DIFFERENT QUANTIZERS FOR H- $\Sigma\Delta$

Operations	Standard quantizer	Standard with B&B	Fast H- $\Sigma\Delta$
Additions	17	7	5
Subtractions	34	14	0
Multiplications	34	14	6
Comparisons	16	8	11
ROMs	No	No	11-bit
Total	101	43	22

B. DC-Bus Balancing Algorithm

The neutral-point current, i_0 , is determined by the interaction between the phase currents and the converter's switching states. This relationship is defined as:

$$i_0 = \sum_{x \in \{a,b,c\}} (1 - |v'_x|) \cdot i_x \quad (26)$$

where i_x denotes the phase current and $v'_x \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ represents the switching state for phase x .

Equation (26) defines the direction of the NP current as a function of the selected switching state, v'_x , and the polarity of the phase currents. Knowing the sign of i_0 and the error between the capacitor voltages on the bus ($v_{CH} - v_{CL}$), we can determine whether the vector to be applied by the converter will balance, unbalance, or have no effect on the bus capacitors. In the three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, the vectors corresponding to sectors B_1 to B_6 are chosen based on the knowledge of phase currents and the impact of the vector on the neutral point. For instance, if during a sampling cycle, the reference vector is located within B_1 and the lower dc-link capacitor of the converter has a higher voltage level than the upper one ($v_{CL} > v_{CH}$), the NP current must be positive ($i_0 > 0$) to decrease the NP voltage. Therefore, vector 0-1-1 should be selected if i_a is positive. Otherwise, vector 100 is selected. However, medium vectors, i.e., those in sectors B_8 , B_{10} , B_{12} , B_{14} , B_{16} , and B_{18} , also unbalance the DC bus. To avoid the imbalances caused by these vectors, they are applied only if they help balance the DC bus. If the vector unbalances the bus, the nearest long vector is applied instead, as these vectors do not affect the bus. To determine the nearest long vector, part of the previous comparisons are used, specifically Bits 2, 1, and 0. These bits are the address of the ROM shown in Table III. For example, if the reference vector is in B_8 and the NP current must be positive ($i_0 > 0$), the vector 10-1 should be applied if i_b is positive. Otherwise, the vector corresponds to the sector B_7 or B_9 . If Bit 1 = 1, the vector 11-1 is applied, while if Bit 1 = 0, the vector 1-1-1 is selected. Figure 5 illustrates the control system of the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, including the DC-bus balancing algorithm.

In summary, the proposed algorithm actively regulates the neutral current to compensate for voltage imbalances. Specifically, in each H- $\Sigma\Delta$ cycle, if $v_{CH} < v_{CL}$, the modulation injects a positive current ($i_0 > 0$) to discharge the lower capacitor relative to the upper one. In contrast, if $v_{CH} > v_{CL}$, a negative current ($i_0 < 0$) is synthesized. In steady-state operation ($v_{CL} \approx v_{CH}$), or when no effective balancing vectors are available, the algorithm ensures a zero neutral current. Hence,

Fig. 5. Control scheme of the proposed three-level fast H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategy.

TABLE III
LONG VECTOR SECTOR IN H- $\Sigma\Delta$

Bit 2	Bit 1	Bit 0	Sector
0	0	0	B_{15}
0	1	0	B_{13}
0	1	1	B_{11}
1	0	0	B_{17}
1	0	1	B_7
1	1	1	B_9

this strategy effectively balances the DC-link voltages and virtually eliminates the low-frequency oscillations associated with NP currents.

It is worth noting that the proposed neutral-point balancing algorithm and fast quantizer can be integrated into a single 15-bit ROM. By using four additional inputs, namely, the signs of the output currents and the DC-link voltage error ($v_{CH} - v_{CL}$), the explicit i_0 evaluation in (26) is bypassed, implicitly encoding the balancing logic. Although presented separately for clarity, this unified approach effectively minimises logic resource utilisation in practice.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section evaluates the impact of the proposed three-level H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique on the T-type converter, which is constructed using GaN and SiC transistors (see Fig. 1). To assess the effects of the proposed modulation strategy, the results are compared with those obtained using the Modified Sinusoidal PWM (M-SPWM), Carrier-Based PWM (CB-PWM) [20], and Novel Pulse Sequence DPWM (NPSDPWM) [21] techniques.

In $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations, the switching frequency (f_{sw}) is variable and is defined as:

$$f_{sw} = \frac{f_s}{n}, \quad (27)$$

where f_s represents the sampling frequency, and n is an integer such that $n \geq 2 \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (i.e., $n = 2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty$).

For comparison purposes, this article employs the maximum switching frequency (f_{max}) as a key parameter. In $\Sigma\Delta$ techniques, the maximum switching frequency is always

half the sampling frequency ($f_{max} = f_s/2$). This intrinsic boundary prevents any unexpected high-frequency burst events that could induce localised thermal runaway, ensuring the safe operation of the transistors. Whereas, in M-SPWM, CB-PWM, and NSPD PWM techniques, the maximum switching frequency equals the sampling frequency ($f_{max} = f_s$). The modulation index is defined as $m = m_a\sqrt{3}/2$, where m_a is the original modulation index. Consequently, m lies within the range $[0, 1]$.

The studied T-type converter is modelled using MATLAB/Simulink and the PLECS Blockset. The rated power of the converter is 15 kW, with a DC bus voltage of 1000 V. The AC-side currents are maintained constant at their rated values of 40 A (rms). The GaN transistor model GS66516T and the SiC module CAB450M12XM3 are used to simulate the converter switches. The GaN transistors feature a maximum drain-source voltage (V_{ds}) of 650 V and a continuous drain current (I_d) of 60 A. The SiC module has a maximum drain-source voltage (V_{ds}) of 1200 V and a continuous drain current (I_d) of 450 A. The PLECS software is utilized to calculate the losses based on the thermal datasheet and the equations provided by the manufacturer.

A. Efficiency Analysis

The efficiency of the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation technique is evaluated under various operating conditions. This modulation strategy utilizes the fast quantizer introduced in Section II-A. Figure 6 illustrates the ratio of the total converter losses by comparing the CB-PWM, the NSPD PWM, and H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategies to the M-SPWM. Fig. 6(a) depicts the loss ratio between the CB-PWM and the M-SPWM. The results indicate that the total losses of the CB-PWM approach are consistently lower than those of the M-SPWM at all operating conditions. At low modulation indices, up to $m = 0.4$, the loss ratio remains between approximately 0.2 and 0.3. However, at higher modulation indices, this ratio increases, reaching values of approximately 0.6 or higher. In certain operating points, the ratio can increase to as much as 0.85. Fig. 6(b) presents the loss ratio between the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation and the M-SPWM. In this case, the losses are generally lower but tend to increase for modulation indices close to $m = 0.5$. When there is no phase shift between voltage and current, the losses range approximately from 0.15 to 0.35, with the most critical points observed at modulation indices close to $m = 0.5$. However, as the current phase angle increases, the losses in these modulation indices also grow, even exceeding those of the M-SPWM under extreme conditions with phase shifts of 180° . Nevertheless, the losses associated with H- $\Sigma\Delta$ remain lower under all operating conditions, except for these extreme cases. Furthermore, Fig. 6(c) displays the loss ratio for the NSPD PWM strategy. This technique also consistently exhibits lower losses than the M-SPWM across the entire operating range, maintaining a ratio of approximately 0.6 for low phase-shift angles. However, under significant phase shifts, this ratio increases, reaching up to 0.96 at the most critical operating points. Finally, a comparison of these techniques reveals that CB-PWM and H- $\Sigma\Delta$ generate similar losses at low modulation indices, both outperforming the NSPD PWM in this

Fig. 6. Ratios of total losses at $f_{max} = 200$ kHz. (a) CB-PWM to M-SPWM. (b) H- $\Sigma\Delta$ to M-SPWM. (c) NSPD PWM to M-SPWM.

region. For modulation indices exceeding $m = 0.4$, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation generally outperforms both the CB-PWM and the NSPD PWM, except in scenarios with phase shifts greater than 80° or less than -80° , and modulation indices near $m = 0.5$. Hence, H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation demonstrates superior efficiency under most operating conditions, particularly at higher modulation indices. Moreover, its losses are more than 50% lower compared to those observed with M-SPWM in the majority of cases.

B. DC-bus balancing

In this section, we analyse the maximum low-frequency voltage oscillations that occur at the midpoint of the DC. The parameter under analysis is the normalized ripple amplitude [20], which is defined as

$$\frac{\Delta V_{NPn}}{2} = \frac{\Delta V_{NP}/2}{I_{RMS}/(f_{out} \cdot C)}, \quad (28)$$

where ΔV_{NP} represents the low-frequency peak-to-peak voltage ripple, I_{RMS} is the root-mean-square value of the output currents, f_{out} is the output frequency, and C is the capacitance of one half of the DC-link.

Figure 7 illustrates the oscillations observed in the DC bus for the modulation techniques studied. Fig. 7(a) depicts the oscillations produced by the M-SPWM modulation. In this modulation scheme, the oscillations range approximately from 0.001 to 0.03 and are proportional to the modulation index. The phase shift between voltage and current also influences the oscillations, as they increase significantly for phase shift values close to 80° . Fig. 7(b) shows the oscillations caused by the CB-PWM modulation. In general, this modulation exhibits lower oscillations compared to M-SPWM, as it incorporates a balancing algorithm. The oscillations begin to increase for modulation indices above 0.5 and are particularly prominent for phase shifts close to 80° . Fig. 7(c) shows the oscillations generated by the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation. This modulation technique exhibits virtually no oscillations at all operating points, due to the balancing algorithm described in Section II-B. Finally, Fig. 7(d) presents the oscillations resulting from the NSPDPWM strategy. This technique demonstrates robust NP balancing capabilities, exhibiting lower oscillations than the CB-PWM up to $m = 0.8$. However, beyond this modulation index, its behaviour is similar to that of the CB-PWM, with oscillations also peaking for phase shifts near 80° . Consequently, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation demonstrates the most effective balance of the DC bus oscillations among all the studied techniques, as it is the only strategy that maintains near-zero oscillations across all operating points.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A modular hybrid T-type power converter was developed to perform the experimental analysis. Each converter phase is equipped with its power and control PCB. The prototype integrates SiC MOSFETs (SCTH70N120G2V-7) rated for a maximum voltage of 1200 V and a nominal drain current of 90 A, along with GaN e-HEMTs (GS66516T) rated for a maximum drain-source voltage of 650 V and a nominal current of 60 A. The converter is designed for power levels up to 15 kW. Fig. 8 shows the hybrid T-type converter. The experimental setup includes a single-phase Line Impedance Stabilisation Network (LISN, Electro-Metrics EM-7820) on the DC side, powered by an isolated 400-Vdc source. On the AC side, there was a three-phase series-connected RL load with $R = 68 \Omega$ and $L = 1.55$ mH. Voltage and current measurements were performed using a high-resolution oscilloscope (Agilent InfiniiVision MSO7104A) with a bandwidth of 1 GHz and a sampling rate of 4 GS/s. The Total Harmonic

Fig. 7. Normalized low-frequency neutral-point voltage amplitudes. (a) M-SPWM. (b) CB-PWM. (c) H- $\Sigma\Delta$. (d) NSPDPWM.

Distortion (THD) analysis was based on current measurements acquired using Keysight N2783B current probes, which offer a bandwidth of 100 MHz. The common-mode voltage was measured using a high-voltage differential probe (PMK BumbleBee) with a bandwidth of 400 MHz. Efficiencies were quantified through a digital power meter (Yokogawa WT1600)

Fig. 8. Hybrid three-level T-type power converter prototype.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. View of the experimental setup. (a) Setup schematic. (b) Photograph of the implemented setup.

featuring a 1 MHz bandwidth. All modulation schemes were implemented using a dSPACE DS1006 platform and a DS5203 FPGA board. Digital low-pass filtering was applied to the measured phase currents to enhance the robustness of the NP-balancing algorithm and mitigate noise-induced inaccuracies during zero-crossings. Figure 9 illustrates the experimental setup.

A. Steady-State Analysis and Harmonic Distortion

To compare the spectral performance and signal quality of the modulation techniques, Fig. 10 presents the experimental frequency spectra, the time-domain line voltages, and the output currents for M-SPWM, CB-PWM, and the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$. Fig. 10(a) depicts the frequency spectra of the output currents (i_a) obtained at $f_{\max} = 200$ kHz and $m = 0.9$.

To compare the spectral performance of the three modulation strategies, a limit is established considering $100 \text{ dB}\mu\text{A}$ for harmonics up to 2 kHz (derived from IEC 61000-3-2 [22]) and $60 \text{ dB}\mu\text{A}$ for the frequency range from 150 kHz to 1 MHz, corresponding to typical peak limits found in vehicular and industrial standards (IEC 55025) for broadband noise [23]. Since no specific EMI standards regulate the 2 kHz to 150 kHz band, this paper applies a logarithmic interpolation between the aforementioned frequency thresholds. It should be noted that these limits are used strictly as a reference for relative spectral comparison, not for standard compliance. The M-SPWM modulation exhibits negligible harmonic content at low frequencies; however, significant harmonics appear at the switching frequency and its multiples, thus exceeding the peak limits of IEC 55025. The CB-PWM technique demonstrates similar behaviour. Although its low-frequency harmonics are higher, they remain within the considered limits. In the high-frequency range, CB-PWM generates a larger number of harmonics that exceed the limit compared to M-SPWM, although their individual amplitudes are generally lower. Finally, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation presents the most different spectral profile. Its low-frequency harmonics are comparable to those of the other two techniques and remain below the limits. In the unregulated region (from 2 to 150 kHz), the harmonics produced by this modulation are higher due to its variable switching frequency. However, above 150 kHz, all harmonics generated remain below the $60 \text{ dB}\mu\text{A}$ limit, which makes it the superior modulation strategy in terms of high-frequency EMI mitigation. Fig. 10(b) illustrates the line voltages (V_{ab}) generated by the three analysed techniques. The M-SPWM strategy exhibits a superior waveform quality compared to its counterparts. Although some distortion is observable in all waveforms, it is more noticeable in the CB-PWM and H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations. In the CB-PWM case, this distortion arises from the phase-clamping mechanism employed to mitigate DC-link midpoint oscillations and minimise switching losses. Nevertheless, in the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique, the distortion is a consequence of the harmonics spreading over a wide frequency range. Furthermore, $\Sigma\Delta$ modulations may involve the simultaneous switching of two phases, thereby inducing voltage spikes. Finally, Fig. 10(c) depicts the converter output currents. All modulation techniques produce highly sinusoidal currents, validating their proper operation. The distortion levels are comparable across all current waveforms. However, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation exhibits a slightly higher ripple than its counterparts, due to the higher spectral content present in the 2–150 kHz frequency band. To quantify this spectral content, the Total Band-Limited Distortion ($TBLD$) is defined as:

$$TBLD(\%) = \sqrt{\sum_{n=41}^{3000} \left(\frac{I_n}{I_1}\right)^2 + \sum_{n=40}^{3000} \left(\frac{I_{i,n}}{I_1}\right)^2} \cdot 100 \quad (29)$$

where I_n and $I_{i,n}$ are the harmonic and interharmonic currents within this band, respectively, and I_1 is the fundamental current. The calculated $TBLD$ values are 1.71%, 2.04%, and 3.81% for M-SPWM, CB-PWM, and H- $\Sigma\Delta$, respectively. This highlights a clear downside of the proposed modulation: while it successfully mitigates emissions above 150 kHz, it

Fig. 10. Experimental results at 200 kHz and $m=0.9$. (a) Spectrum of current i_a . (b) Line voltage V_{ab} . (c) Output current i_a .

Fig. 11. Experimental converter THD at 200 kHz.

concentrates more spectral energy in the 2–150 kHz range, leading to the observed higher current ripple.

To evaluate the quality of the modulations at low frequencies, the current THD produced by the proposed H-ΣΔ technique was compared with that of the M-SPWM and CB-PWM strategies. The THD values were calculated according to the methodology specified by the IEC 61000-3-2 standard; consequently, this analysis is restricted to the first 40 harmonics [22]. Fig. 11 presents the experimental THD values obtained for the different techniques across a range of operating points. In general, the THD decreases for all strategies as the modulation index (m) increases. Nevertheless, some differences are observed at specific operating points.

Fig. 12. Experimental common-mode voltage spectra at 200 kHz and $m=0.9$.

At low modulation indices (up to $m = 0.5$), the M-SPWM technique produces the highest THD levels, followed by CB-PWM. Beyond this modulation index, CB-PWM exhibits higher THD values than M-SPWM, a behaviour attributed to its phase-clamping mechanism. In particular, the H-ΣΔ modulation achieves lower THD than the other techniques across the entire operating range, although the performance gap between the strategies generally narrows as m increases.

B. Experimental Common-mode Voltage

Another critical parameter in the comparison of modulation strategies is the common-mode voltage. Figure 12 depicts the CMV frequency spectra for the three investigated techniques at $f_{\max} = 200$ kHz and $m = 0.9$. The M-SPWM and CB-PWM

Fig. 13. Experimental converter efficiency curves at 200 kHz.

TABLE IV
EXPERIMENTAL H- $\Sigma\Delta$ AVERAGE SWITCHING FREQUENCY

Index (m)	H- $\Sigma\Delta$ (kHz)
0.2	75.64
0.3	116.48
0.4	86.68
0.5	87.85
0.6	141.58
0.7	100.78
0.8	75.75
0.9	103.00

modulations exhibit similar spectral profiles, characterised by voltage peaks concentrated at the switching frequency and its multiples. However, the M-SPWM technique generates higher peak voltages compared to CB-PWM. In contrast, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation exhibits a different spectral characteristic. As $\Sigma\Delta$ techniques inherently distribute switching harmonics across a broad spectrum, significant spikes are absent from the CMV. Consequently, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation produces the lowest overall CMV levels among the investigated techniques. Above 10 MHz, the disparities between the techniques decrease, resulting in negligible differences among the strategies above this frequency.

C. Experimental Efficiency

To evaluate the power loss reduction achievable with the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, the efficiency of the different techniques was measured. Figure 13 illustrates the converter efficiency at $f_{\max} = 200$ kHz. While the efficiency of all modulation strategies increases with the modulation index, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique consistently exhibits the highest performance, followed by CB-PWM and, finally, M-SPWM. This performance ranking is due to the distinct switching behaviours of the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ and CB-PWM strategies. The first operates with a variable switching frequency, avoiding unnecessary commutations and minimising switching losses. In contrast, CB-PWM employs a phase-clamping mechanism that also reduces switching losses, but at the cost of increased THD (see Fig. 11). The M-SPWM technique operates at a fixed switching frequency, resulting in the highest losses among the tested modulations. The difference between the modulation techniques is particularly

Fig. 14. Dynamics of the DC-link voltage at $m = 0.9$. (a) CB-PWM. (b) H- $\Sigma\Delta$.

pronounced at modulation indices between 0.4 and 0.5, where the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategy is clearly superior. For indices above 0.6, the efficiency gap narrows, so the established performance behaviour remains consistent. Specifically, at a modulation index of 0.9, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique achieves an efficiency of 95.92%, compared to a slightly lower 95.7% for CB-PWM and 95.1% for M-SPWM.

To provide a complete overview of the switching behaviour of the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation, Table IV presents its measured average switching frequency at $f_{\max} = 200$ kHz. As can be observed, the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ exhibits a variable average frequency, which is consistently lower than f_{\max} . Furthermore, comparing Table IV with Fig. 13 reveals a clear lack of correlation between the average switching frequency and the converter's overall efficiency for the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique, a behaviour that is entirely consistent with previous studies in the literature [16].

D. Neutral-Point Voltage Oscillations

The three modulation strategies are compared regarding the DC-link midpoint voltage oscillations. Fig. 14 illustrates the voltage dynamics across the DC-link capacitors. The output frequency was set to 10 Hz to emphasise the inherent low-frequency voltage oscillations. The tests were conducted at a maximum switching frequency $f_{\max} = 200$ kHz and a modulation index $m = 0.9$.

Figure 14 shows the DC-link capacitor voltages obtained using M-SPWM, CB-PWM and the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation. Fig. 14(a) depicts the midpoint voltages using the M-SPWM technique. Although the DC link remains balanced on average, significant voltage oscillations are observed, reaching amplitudes of approximately 25 V. Fig. 14(b) illustrates

the voltage behaviour using the CB-PWM strategy. In this instance, the DC link is also balanced, but the oscillations are reduced to a maximum of 8 V. In contrast, Fig. 14(c) presents the voltage ripples generated by the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation. Using the proposed technique, oscillations are negligible, always remaining below 5 V. Consequently, the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation demonstrates a superior capability to mitigate low-frequency voltage oscillations compared with PWM strategies.

V. CONCLUSION

This article proposes and experimentally validates a novel hexagonal sigma-delta modulation technique designed for three-level T-type converters utilising wide-bandgap power semiconductors. Furthermore, the implementation incorporates a fast-processing quantizer that significantly reduces the computational burden, facilitating the deployment of the algorithm on real-time control platforms. The effectiveness of the proposed technique is demonstrated by experimental results obtained from a SiC/GaN-based prototype. The H- $\Sigma\Delta$ modulation was compared against conventional M-SPWM and CB-PWM strategies. Results indicate that the proposed modulation exhibits the highest efficiency across the entire operating range, peaking at 95.92% at a modulation index of 0.9. This performance enhancement is attributed to the variable switching frequency inherent to the $\Sigma\Delta$ loop, which avoids unnecessary switchings and minimises losses without incurring the THD penalty associated with the phase-clamping mechanism of CB-PWM. From a thermomechanical reliability perspective, the fact that the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ effectively reduces overall losses directly implies a lower mean junction temperature compared to fixed-frequency techniques. As confirmed by recent studies on SiC module reliability [24], minimising the average junction temperature and thermal gradients is critical to mitigating thermal stress and, ultimately, extending the devices' operational lifespan. Regarding power quality and electromagnetic interference, the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ technique exhibits a superior spectral profile. The experimental analysis confirms that the proposed modulation is consistent with the emission envelopes of the IEC 61000-3-2 standard up to 2 kHz while maintaining high-frequency content below the reference thresholds derived from IEC 55025. Although the H- $\Sigma\Delta$ strategy may lead to an increase in spectral density within the 2–150 kHz range, a common trade-off in variable-frequency modulations, its inherent spread-spectrum characteristic effectively produces the lowest CMV levels among the studied techniques, as it eliminates the significant voltage spikes observed in PWM-based methods. Concerning DC-link voltage ripple, the proposed modulation virtually eliminates low-frequency oscillations. In conclusion, the proposed H- $\Sigma\Delta$ offers a superior trade-off between efficiency, harmonic distortion, and EMI suppression, making it a highly attractive alternative for high-frequency wide-bandgap T-type converters.

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